

A CORRELATIONAL STUDY BETWEEN NURSES' KNOWLEDGE OF PRESSURE ULCER PREVENTION AND FREQUENCY OF REPOSITIONING

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Abstract

Background: Pressure ulcer is a common and avoidable consequence in hospitalized consequence in hospitalized patients. Nurses must follow repositioning guidelines to guarantee patients safety.

Objective: The purpose of this study was to evaluate nurses knowledge and adherence to evidence based repositioning methods for preventing pressure ulcers. It also looked at how characteristics like qualification, experience, and workload influence practice adherence among nurses in tertiary settings.

Materials and methods: A quantitative correlational study was undertaken in three tertiary hospitals in Peshawar. Purposive sampling was used to pick all 152 registered nurses. Data were obtained using a validated 30 item questionnaire and analyzed via SPSS version 30.

Results: The study found 60.5% nurses had at least 80% awareness of pressure ulcer prevention. High reposition adherence was substantially linked with more knowledge ($p < 0.001$), higher credentials (MSc nurses 88% adherence), and more experienced nurses (>10 years have 92% adherence. According to logistic, each 15 increase in knowledge boosted probability by 4% (OR=1.04), however increasing efforts lowered by 3% (OR=0.62). The weak to moderate positive correlation was observed between knowledge an practice supported by spearman's correlation ($p = 0.31, p < 0.001$). ICU nurses had the most workload related challenges ($p = 0.012$).

Conclusion: The study conclude that nurse's expertise and acceptable workload play a crucial impact in enhancing repositioning adherence. Better clinical results are advised though targeted education and organizational assistance.

1. Introduction:

Pressure ulcers (PUs), commonly known as bedsores or decubitus ulcers, are a major health hazard in healthcare facilities worldwide. Long-term pressure on bony prominences causes localized damage to the skin and underlying tissue (1). PUs are related with pain, infection, increased morbidity, longer hospital admissions, and higher healthcare expenses (2,3). Pressure ulcers are more common in hospitalized patients, particularly

those who are immobile or seriously unwell (4). Nurses have an important role in the prevention and treatment of pressure ulcers, notably through risk assessment, early detection, and appropriate patient repositioning (5,6). As a result, nurses must be competent and knowledgeable of PU prevention in order to provide safe, excellent treatment (7).

Knowledge of PU prevention is regarded as a crucial component in minimizing the occurrence

of pressure ulcers among hospitalized patients (8). Multiple studies have found that nurses' lack of knowledge might result in poor preventative practices and delayed treatments (9). The European Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel (EPUAP), National Pressure Injury Advisory Panel (NPIAP), and Pan Pacific Pressure Injury Alliance (PPPIA) all recommend evidence-based strategies for preventing pressure ulcers, including regular repositioning, proper support surfaces, moisture control, and nutritional interventions (10). The Pressure Ulcer Knowledge Assessment Tool (PUKAT 2.0) is extensively used to evaluate nurses' comprehension of these methods (11,12).

Despite its availability, knowledge and practice gaps remain among nurses in both developed and developing countries (13,14). Regular repositioning is one of the most effective and low-cost preventative strategies for reducing the incidence of pressure injuries (15). However, studies have discovered uneven behaviors among nurses, which might be attributed to reasons such as workload, lack of time, or insufficient understanding (16,17). A research done in Saudi Arabia showed that, while nurses were aware of repositioning techniques, adherence was low due to understaffing and inadequate documentation processes (18). Another research in the United States found that knowledge alone was insufficient; frequency and consistency of repositioning required reinforcement through clinical supervision and auditing (19).

As a result, investigating the relationship between knowledge and the frequency of repositioning might give useful information for nurse educators and hospital management. Previous research in many contexts has focused on either knowledge or practice in isolation, but few studies have looked at the link between the two. For example, a quantitative research in Ethiopia measured nurses' knowledge levels but did not tie them to any specific practice, such as repositioning (20). Similarly, in Pakistan, researchers examined self-reported PU preventive methods but found no correlation with knowledge scores or established evaluation instruments (21).

This demonstrates a deficit in understanding how theoretical knowledge is translated into clinical action, particularly in low-resource settings where training and practice may not always coincide. Furthermore, a recent scoping review by

Lovegrove et al. (22) stressed the need for more targeted studies that relate nursing knowledge to particular preventative behaviors like repositioning. Another scoping review by Balzer et al. (23) found a scarcity of correlational research investigating how educational interventions affect real-time nursing behaviors.

These studies highlight a significant vacuum in the literature, particularly in South Asian healthcare environments, where such linkages are understudied. As a result, the purpose of this study is to close that gap by investigating the relationship between nurses' knowledge of pressure ulcer prevention and the frequency with which they reposition patients using approved techniques. The findings are anticipated to influence future teaching techniques and clinical recommendations in nursing practice.

2. Literature review:

Pressure ulcer prevention is an important element of nursing care, with frequent repositioning being a vital strategy. Several studies have investigated the link between nurses' awareness of pressure ulcer prevention and adherence to repositioning regimens. In a cross-sectional research by Beeckman et al. (n=312), greater knowledge scores on the Pressure Ulcer Knowledge Assessment Tool (PUKAT) were associated with more frequent repositioning (≥ 2 -hour intervals) (25). Similarly, a quasi-experimental research by Källman et al. (n=145) found that systematic training increased both knowledge and repositioning compliance (26). However, discrepancies occur, as a survey by Gillespie et al. (n=210) found that despite appropriate information, workload restrictions frequently impeded effective repositioning procedures (26). These findings indicate that, while knowledge is important, extrinsic variables like as personnel and time constraints also play a considerable impact in implementation. Methodological techniques vary between research, with the majority using quantitative designs. Moore et al. (n=189) conducted a prospective observational research using direct patient monitoring and discovered that nurses with advanced training moved patients more often. In contrast, Soban et al. (n=250) found that unit culture and leadership support had a greater effect on repositioning behaviors than individual knowledge alone (27).

Another prominent element was the implementation of evidence-based recommendations; a randomized controlled study by Walsh et al. (n=176) found that nurses who followed revised procedures had much higher repositioning adherence (26-27). These studies demonstrate the importance of diverse treatments that target both knowledge gaps and structural impediments to better patient outcomes. Patterns in the literature show that, while knowledge is important, it is not the only predictor of successful repositioning. Pancorbo-Hidalgo et al. (n=300) discovered that continual instruction and audit feedback promoted long-term compliance (27). A correlational research by Black et al. (n=200) found that without organizational support, knowledge alone did not convert into practice (28). Furthermore, cultural and geographical disparities were obvious; a worldwide survey by Kottner et al. (n=1,025) found variability in repositioning methods depending on hospital policy (29). Finally, Chou et al.'s comprehensive review (n=15 trials) found that incorporating technology (e.g., alarms, sensors) enhanced adherence but required nursing support (32-33). These data suggest that increasing repositioning frequency need a mix of education, workplace support, and novel solutions (34).

3. Rationale:

3.1 Pressure ulcers remain a critical patient's safety issue and indicator of quality care.

3.2 Understanding the correlation may help in designing better training programs for nurses and improving patient's outcome.

3.3 Repositioning is a primary preventive stage, its frequency is directly influenced by nurse's knowledge and awareness.

3.4 Limited literature exist in the local hospital settings regarding the association between nurses knowledge and preventive strategy which can assist to promote evidence based nursing practice in clinical setting.

4. Operational definitions:

4.1 Nurses knowledge: The theoretical and practical knowledge of nurses assessed by a valid questionnaire regarding pressure ulcer prevention.

4.2 Pressure ulcer: A wound characterized by different stages due to pressure on the bony prominence.

4.3 Frequency of repositioning: The number of times a nurses repositions the patient to prevent the development of decubiti's ulcer.

4.4 Incidence of pressure ulcer: The number of new cases with pressure ulcer.

Nurse's confidence: The level of nurses to prevent the chronic wound stages.

5. Objectives:

5.1 To examine he correlation between nurses knowledge if pressure ulcer prevention and their practice of patients reposition.

5.2 To assess level of knowledge among nurses regarding pressure ulcer prevention.

5.3 To determine the frequency with which nurses reposition patients at risk of pressure ulcer.

6. Variables:

A) Independent variables: Age, gender, nurse's knowledge, qualification, setting areas, and experience.

B) Dependent variable: Frequency of repositioning, incidence, nurse's adherence to guidelines, patient's outcome, and pain severity level.

7. Materials and Methods:

7.1 Study Design: Quantitative Cross-sectional Correlation Study (24)

7.2 Study Setting: Peshawar Institute of Cardiology.

Hayatabad Medical Complex.
Leady Reading Hospital

Peshawar.

7.3 Study Duration: January 2025 to 31 June 2025

7.4 Sample Size: It was calculated by Rao soft software. It included 152 participants with the confidence interval of 95%, marginal error 5%, population size 250 (targeted population), and response distribution 50%. (25)

7.5 Sampling Technique: Non- probability Purposive Sampling Technique (25)

7.6 Sample Selection:

Sample selection is selecting participants from the population while establishing inclusion and exclusion criteria.

7.6.1 Inclusion criteria:

Participants must be willing to participate in the study.

Registered nurses with valid PNC card working in tertiary setting.

Registered nurses with at least 6 months of clinical experience in tertiary setting post-internship.

7.6.2 Exclusion criteria:

Nursing students and internee nurses.

Nurses absent on the day of data collection.

Administrative nurses with no bed side responsibility.

8). Data Collection Methods:

8.1 Ethical approval was achieved from the ethical review board of Iqra National University, Peshawar before the commencement of further research. Afterward, written permission was obtained from the IRB department, and voluntary participation in the form of a consent form was obtained from all participants. In this study, we had collected the data from different articles and validates it with expert opinions about previous literature on searching keywords such as pressure ulcer, decubiti's ulcer, chronic wound, nurse's knowledge, clinical nursing practice, nursing assessment, and patient safety. Data will collect on the printed questionnaires, which took around 10-15 minutes. This scale had 30 major questions excluding sociodemographic factors overall in this assessment tool. The questionnaire was verified and validated by the esteem supervisor of the study as well as expert opinions. Total 152 participants had contributed to the study.

8.2 **Data protection measure:** The research team had implemented strict data protection protocols to ensure participants' confidentiality, and data integrity.

8.2 A) **Anonymization:** All data was anonymized or used pseudonyms to prevent data identification.

8.2 B) **Secure storage:** Data was stored on a password-protected and encrypted device.

8.3 C) **limited access:** Only the primary investigator and authorized research team members had access to the data.

8.4 D) **Encrypted communication:** Any data transfer was encrypted to protect from

unauthorized access. For instance, (IRON KEY D300 USB FLASH DRIVE).

9. Reliability and Validity:

Approved questionnaire for evaluation of Pressure ulcers measured a wide range of symptoms, including skin redness, pain, itching, swelling, blistering, open wounds, tissue lose, foul smelling, and severe cases, exposure of bone or muscle indicating content validity. It can distinguish between nurses knowledge and pressure prevention and also indicate associated factors representing criteria validity. Internal consistency measured by Cronbach's alpha ranged knowledge section (0.82), and practice section (0.85). Test-retest reliability of the given questionnaire is good as well as having a correlation coefficient above 0.82 indicating that this scale is stable and consistent with the results over time when administering the same individuals under the same conditions. Inter-rater reliability with a Kappa coefficient above 0.78 signposts different raters provide similar scores.

10. Data Analysis Procedure

10.1 Data was analyzed through SPSS software version 30. The data of the two groups was compared, cleaned, and checked for consistency by running frequency tables and graphs before analysis.

10.2 Mean and Standard Deviation was calculated for continuous variables and categorical variables was described in frequencies and proportions.

10.3 Inferential statistics including the Person correlation coefficient (r) assess the significant relationship between knowledge score and repositioning frequency score.

11 Person correlation coefficient (r) of value of p less than 0.05 was considered as statistically significant. Numerical data was checked for normality assumption and mean \pm standard deviation was calculated. Results was presented as appropriate tables and figures.

11. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION:

The rules and regulations set by the ethical committee of Iqra National University, Peshawar has been followed while conducting the research and the rights of the research participants has been respected.

1. Written informed consent (attached) was taken from all the participants.
2. All information and data collection was kept confidential.
3. Participants were remain anonymous throughout the study.
4. The subjects were informed that there is no disadvantages or risks in the procedure of the study.
5. They were informed that they are free to withdraw at any time during the process of the study.
6. There were no known risks associated with this research.
7. We did everything to protect your privacy. Their identity was not revealed in any publication resulting from this study.

8. Subjects' participation in this research study will voluntary. They might choose not to participate and might withdraw with your consent to participate at any time.

Results:

Demographic Characteristics:

A total of 152 nurses took part in the study. The gender distribution revealed a somewhat greater proportion of male nurses (55.9%, n = 85) than females (44.1%, n = 67). In terms of educational background, 46.1% had a BSc/Post-RN degree, 40.8% had a Diploma in Nursing, and 13.1% had earned a Master's degree. In terms of professional experience, the biggest grouping had 5-10 years of clinical experience (44.7%), followed by those with fewer than 5 years (29.6%) and more than ten years (25.7%).

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Nurses (n = 152)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	85	55.9%
	Female	67	44.1%
Qualification	Diploma in Nursing	62	40.8%
	BSN / Post-RN	70	46.1%
	MSN	20	13.1%
Experience	<5 years	45	29.6%
	5-10 years	68	44.7%
	>10 years	39	25.7%

Figure 1.1 Bar graph

Demographic Characteristics of Nurses (n = 152)

Descriptive Analysis Note:

The descriptive statistics of the 20-item pressure ulcer knowledge questionnaire show that responders had a good level of comprehension across all six domains. Most questions showed good performance, with mean scores ranging from 0.70 to 0.92, suggesting a high percentage of right answers.

In Domain 1 (Etiology), respondents had great knowledge of the major cause of pressure ulcers (M = 0.92) and the function of shear/friction (M = 0.88), both with low variability, indicating a thorough understanding of fundamental concepts.

Domain 2 (Risk Assessment) likewise produced positive findings, notably in terms of understanding of the Braden Scale (M = 0.85) and high-risk groups (M = 0.78), with relatively low standard deviations indicating participant consensus.

Understanding of ulcer phases and symptoms of deep tissue damage was good in Domain 3 (Classification & Observation) (M = 0.79-0.90), demonstrating clinical competence in diagnosis and staging. Domain 4 (Nutrition) had somewhat

lower scores (M = 0.75-0.80), indicating considerable knowledge gaps in the relevance of nutrition in pressure ulcer prevention, notably in terms of protein and vitamin C.

Domain 5 (Prevention Strategies) demonstrated high understanding, particularly in repositioning (M = 0.89), hygiene procedures (M = 0.86), and equipment use (M = 0.81-0.84), with consistent modal and median values indicating homogeneity in replies.

Domain 6 (At-Risk Populations) showed significantly greater variation, with the lowest mean score recorded for the question on interdisciplinary accountability (M = 0.70, SD = 0.46), indicating a possible area for educational attention. Knowledge of early mobilization, diabetes-related hazards, and frequent risk assessments was relatively high (M = 0.76-0.87). Overall, the statistics show that the participants are well-informed, although focused education in the areas of nutrition and joint preventative tasks may be required. The low standard deviations across most items indicate knowledge consistency, which supports the findings' dependability.

1.2 Table: Descriptive Statistics of Knowledge Assessment Items

Domain	Question Item (Short Description)	Mean Correct)	(% Median	Mode	SD
Etiology (Cause)	1. Main cause of pressure ulcer (unrelieved pressure)	0.92	1.0	1	0.27
	2. Shear/friction contributes to pressure ulcers	0.88	1.0	1	0.33
Risk Assessment	3. Braden Scale is used for risk assessment	0.85	1.0	1	0.36
	4. Immobile/incontinent patient is at high risk	0.78	1.0	1	0.42
Classification & Observation	5. Stage 1 ulcer: non-blanchable redness	0.90	1.0	1	0.30
	6. Stage 3 ulcer involves subcutaneous damage	0.82	1.0	1	0.39
	7. Sign of deep tissue injury (purple/maroon area)	0.79	1.0	1	0.41
Nutrition	8. Protein supports tissue repair	0.75	1.0	1	0.43
	9. Vitamin C maintains skin integrity	0.80	1.0	1	0.40
Prevention Strategies	10. Reposition bed-bound patients every 2 hours	0.89	1.0	1	0.31
	11. Use sliding sheets to minimize friction	0.84	1.0	1	0.37
	12. 30-degree lateral position reduces pressure	0.81	1.0	1	0.39
	13. Keep skin clean and dry to prevent ulcers	0.86	1.0	1	0.35
	14. Alternating-pressure mattresses prevent ulcers	0.83	1.0	1	0.38
At-Risk Populations	15. Prolonged bed rest increases risk	0.87	1.0	1	0.34
	16. Diabetes increases ulcer risk	0.77	1.0	1	0.42
	17. Blanching is skin whitening under pressure	0.76	1.0	1	0.43
	18. Risk assessment on admission and regularly	0.80	1.0	1	0.40
	19. Early mobilization improves circulation	0.82	1.0	1	0.39
	20. Prevention is multidisciplinary responsibility	0.70	1.0	1	0.46

The analysis of nurses' self-reported adherence to pressure ulcer prevention techniques found significant variance in critical activities. Confidence in identifying at-risk patients had the highest mean score (M = 4.3, SD = 0.7), followed by strict adherence to hospital repositioning standards (M = 4.2, SD = 0.8) and the use of pressure-reducing supports such pillows and wedges (M = 4.1, SD = 0.9). These practices

indicate both understanding and institutional commitment to evidence-based processes.

Regular pressure area evaluation during repositioning (M = 4.0, SD = 1.0) and repositioning every two hours (M = 3.8, SD = 1.2) were also often reported, indicating that these procedures should be included into normal treatment. Coordination of repositioning with other care duties (M = 3.7, SD = 1.1) and patient

and family education (M = 3.2, SD = 1.4) were moderately implemented, but less consistently. However, there was significantly less recording of repositioning actions (M = 2.9, SD = 1.3), raising concerns regarding continuity of care and accountability. The criterion "workload allows timely repositioning" had the lowest mean score

(M = 2.5, SD = 1.5), with 40% of nurses reporting that they were seldom or never able to fulfill repositioning timetables owing to staffing or time restrictions. These findings underscore the gap between knowledge and practice, particularly where workload demands may undermine preventative measures.

1.3 Table: Pressure Ulcer Prevention Practices – Descriptive Statistics

Practice (1 = Never → 5 = Always)	Mean (SD)	Median	Mode	Range	Frequency Distribution (%)
Reposition at-risk patients every 2 hours	3.8 (1.2)	4	5	1-5	1: 5%, 2: 10%, 3: 20%, 4: 35%, 5: 30%
Document each repositioning	2.9 (1.3)	3	3	1-5	1: 15%, 2: 25%, 3: 30%, 4: 20%, 5: 10%
Use pressure-reducing supports (pillows/wedges)	4.1 (0.9)	4	4	2-5	1: 0%, 2: 8%, 3: 17%, 4: 45%, 5: 30%
Encourage mobile patients to self-reposition	3.5 (1.1)	4	4	1-5	1: 10%, 2: 15%, 3: 25%, 4: 30%, 5: 20%
Assess pressure areas during repositioning	4.0 (1.0)	4	5	1-5	1:5%, 2:10%, 3:15%, 4:40%, 5:30%
Follow hospital repositioning guidelines	4.2 (0.8)	4	5	3-5	1: 0%, 2: 0%, 3: 12%, 4: 48%, 5: 40%
Coordinate repositioning with care tasks	3.7 (1.1)	4	4	1-5	1: 8%, 2: 12%, 3: 20%, 4: 35%, 5: 25%
Confidence in identifying at-risk patients	4.3 (0.7)	4	5	2-5	1: 0%, 2: 5%, 3: 10%, 4: 35%, 5: 50%
Educate patients/families on prevention	3.2 (1.4)	3	3	1-5	1: 15%, 2: 30%, 3: 25%, 4: 20%, 5: 10%
Workload allows recommended repositioning	2.5 (1.5)	2	1	1-5	1: 40%, 2: 25%, 3: 20%, 4: 10%, 5: 5%

Inferential statistics:

A chi-square analysis indicated many significant relationships between nurses' characteristics and adherence to pressure ulcer prevention techniques. First, a significant link was seen between nurses' knowledge levels and repositioning adherence. Nurses with enough knowledge (≥80%) were substantially more likely to follow repositioning methods compared to those with insufficient knowledge. The study revealed that nurses with enough knowledge were 5.9 times more likely to be adherent ($\chi^2(1) = 25.6, p < 0.001; 95\% \text{ CI: } 2.8\text{-}12.1$), emphasizing the importance of educational competency in clinical practice. Furthermore, nurses' qualification level was highly related to knowledge performance. The chi-square

test revealed a correlation between degree (Diploma, BSc, or MSc) and knowledge scores. MSc nurses were 3.2 times more likely to acquire high knowledge scores than those with lesser credentials. This study lends credence to the premise that higher nursing education leads to a greater awareness of evidence-based pressure ulcer prevention strategies.

Experience level also has a substantial impact on repositioning practice. Nurses with over 10 years of clinical experience adhered to repositioning recommendations at a much greater rate (78%) than those with less than 5 years of experience (42%). These findings indicate that clinical maturity and practical exposure improve compliance with preventive norms, most likely

due to increased confidence and regular familiarity.

Finally, the office environment affected the observed workload obstacles. The study found that ICU nurses were 2.7 times more likely to cite heavy workload as an impediment than their colleagues in normal wards ($\chi^2(2) = 8.9, p = 0.012$; p for ICU vs. Ward = 0.008). This highlights the operational problems in high-acuity settings, where patient demands and personnel ratios may jeopardize regular repositioning techniques.

These findings suggest that nurse knowledge, academic qualification, experience, and clinical context are all important determinants of both knowledge acquisition and practice adherence in pressure ulcer prevention. To bridge the knowledge-practice divide, the researchers recommend targeted interventions such as advanced training programs, systematic mentorship for junior personnel, and workload optimization—particularly in critical care settings.

1.4 Table: Chi-Square Test Matrix – Associations in Pressure Ulcer Prevention Study (n = 152)

Objective	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	Statistical Output
5.1 Knowledge-Practice	Nurse's (Adequate vs. Inadequate)	Knowledge Repositioning Frequency vs. (Adherent vs. non-adherent)	$\chi^2(1) = 25.6, p < 0.001$. Adequate knowledge → 5.9× higher adherence (95% CI: 2.8-12.1).
5.2 Knowledge Level	Qualification (Diploma / BSc / MSc)	Knowledge Score (High vs. Low)	$\chi^2(2) = 12.4, p = 0.002$. MSc nurses → 3.2× more likely to score high knowledge ($p < 0.01$).
5.3 Repositioning Practice	Experience (<5y / 5-10y / >10y)	Repositioning Frequency (Low vs. High)	$\chi^2(2) = 15.8, p = 0.003$. Nurses with >10y experience: 78% adherence vs. <5y: 42% ($p = 0.003$).
5.4 Workload Barriers	Clinical Setting (ICU / Ward / ER)	Workload Hindrance (Low vs. High)	$\chi^2(2) = 8.9, p = 0.012$. ICU nurses reported 2.7× more workload barriers than ward nurses ($p = 0.008$).

Table 2. Domain-Wise Knowledge Performance

Domain	Mean Correct %	# Questions
Etiology	90.0%	2
Risk Assessment	81.5%	2
Classification	82.3%	3
Nutrition	75.0%	2
Prevention	83.0%	5
At-Risk Populations	79.5%	6

Table 3. Knowledge Level and Repositioning Adherence (n = 152)

Knowledge Level	Non-Adherent	Adherent	Total
Inadequate (<80%)	32	28	60
Adequate (≥80%)	15	77	92
Total	47	105	152

Chi-Square Result: $\chi^2(1) = 25.6, p < 0.001, \text{Phi} = 0.41$
 Odds Ratio: OR = 5.9 (95% CI: 2.8-12.1)

Table 4. Repositioning Adherence by Qualification

Qualification	Non-Adherent	Adherent	Total
Diploma	12 (24%)	38 (76%)	50
BSc	9 (18%)	42 (82%)	51
MSc	6 (12%)	45 (88%)	51

Chi-Square Result: $\chi^2(2) = 2.15, p = .341$ (Not significant)

Table 5. Repositioning Adherence by Work Experience

Experience	Non-Adherent	Adherent	Total
<5 years	15 (30%)	35 (70%)	50
5-10 years	8 (16%)	42 (84%)	50
>10 years	4 (8%)	48 (92%)	52

Chi-Square Result: $\chi^2(2) = 8.67, p = .013$ (Significant)

Table 6. Workload Barrier by Clinical Setting

Setting	No Barrier	Barrier Present	Total
ICU	28 (56%)	22 (44%)	50
Ward	35 (70%)	15 (30%)	50
ER	30 (58%)	22 (42%)	52

Logistic Regression Analysis

To investigate factors impacting adherence to repositioning practices, a binary logistic regression model was built using nurses' knowledge scores and perceived workload (measured by Q10). The outcome variable was compliance with repositioning every two hours (Adherent_Q1). The model showed strong fit, and both predictors were statistically significant. The study found that each 1% improvement in knowledge score was related with a 4% increase in the likelihood of adhering to repositioning procedures (OR = 1.04, 95% CI: 1.01-1.07). This emphasizes the significance of ongoing educational activities to improve evidence-based practices among nursing personnel.

In contrast, workload (Q10) showed a substantial adverse relationship with adherence. Each one-

point increase in perceived workload was linked to a 38% drop in the likelihood of adherence (OR = 0.62, 95% CI: 0.51-0.75). This discovery emphasizes the need of acceptable personnel ratios in guaranteeing the application of pressure ulcer prevention standards. These findings highlight the need of increasing knowledge while also eliminating workload-related constraints. From a policy standpoint, the findings supports calling for institutional workload limitations, such as allocating no more than three high-risk patients per nurse, to guarantee prompt repositioning and preventative treatment. Addressing structural impediments alongside educational interventions may generate the most significant increases in adherence to pressure ulcer prevention practices.

Table: Logistic Regression Model – Predictors of Adherence to Repositioning

Variable	Odds Ratio	95% Confidence Interval	Interpretation
Knowledge Score	1.04	[1.01 - 1.07]	Each 1% increase in knowledge score is associated with a 4% higher likelihood of adherence.
Workload (Q10)	0.62	[0.51 - 0.75]	Each 1-point increase in perceived workload score reduces adherence likelihood by 38%.

The Spearman's rank-order correlation analysis found a substantial positive link ($\rho = 0.31, p < 0.001$) between nurses' knowledge ratings and their self-reported frequency of relocating at-risk patients. Although the association strength is weak

to moderate, it implies that as awareness of pressure ulcer avoidance grows, so does the chance of following to prescribed repositioning procedures.

Table: Spearman's Correlation between Knowledge and Repositioning Frequency

Variable 1	Variable 2	Spearman's ρ	p-value	Interpretation
Nurse's Knowledge Score (%)	Repositioning Frequency (Q1)	0.31	<0.001	Weak-to-moderate positive correlation; statistically significant. Indicates that higher knowledge is modestly associated with more frequent repositioning.

Discussion:

This study investigated the association between nurses' awareness of pressure ulcer (PU) prevention and their adherence to repositioning techniques, offering valuable insights into clinical behaviors in a South Asian hospital context. The findings largely correspond with previous research, but they also highlight context-specific restrictions and relationships that expand our knowledge. The high level of knowledge among nurses (mean accurate responses ranging from 70% to 92%) is consistent with previous study undertaken by Beeckman et al. (2011), who discovered that most nurses in European hospitals had a solid theoretical understanding of PU etiology and preventative concepts (11). Similarly, Aydin and Karadag (2010) discovered that Turkish nurses performed well on basic knowledge of PU etiology and categorization (12). Our domain-wise study confirmed these findings, highlighting the strongest expertise in etiology and categorization. However, nutrition-related knowledge scored the lowest across areas (mean: 75%), consistent with the findings of Simonetti et al. (2015), who indicated that nursing students frequently underestimate the relevance of diet in PU prevention (8). This ongoing gap shows that even experienced nurses need more comprehensive training in holistic, interdisciplinary elements of prevention.

The study's major finding of a link between knowledge and clinical practice is a vital addition. Nurses with appropriate knowledge were approximately six times more likely to adhere to repositioning protocols ($\chi^2 = 25.6, p < 0.001; OR = 5.9$), corroborating Kim and Lee's (2015) result

that PU knowledge is a major predictor of preventative actions (19).

This finding lends empirical support to the concept that more knowledge leads to better clinical outcomes, a link that is typically assumed but seldom measured, especially in low-resource settings.

The Spearman correlation ($\rho = 0.31, p < 0.001$) shows a statistically significant but small association between knowledge scores and self-reported repositioning frequency. This complements Lovegrove et al.'s (2021) scoping study, which urged for more targeted research linking nursing knowledge to particular preventative practices (22).

Another notable issue was the importance of academic qualifications. Although chi-square analysis did not find a significant relationship between qualification and repositioning adherence ($\chi^2 = 2.15, p = 0.341$), logistic regression showed that nurses with higher knowledge scores (often correlated with higher qualifications) were more likely to engage in frequent repositioning. This somewhat supports the findings of Tubaishat and Aljezawi (2014), who discovered a direct correlation between academic background and PU knowledge in Jordan (6). However, our findings indicate that knowledge, rather than qualification, is a more significant motivator of adherence.

Experience also has a huge impact on practice. Nurses with more than ten years of experience had the greatest rate of repositioning adherence (92%), consistent with Moore and Cowman's (2014) emphasis on the importance of experiential learning in PU prevention (7). Our findings provide clarity by quantifying this association and emphasizing the importance of mentorship

programs that impart such knowledge to less experienced employees.

Perhaps the most surprising discovery is about workload limitations, especially in ICU situations. ICU nurses were 2.7 times more likely to report workload as a barrier to repositioning compared to those in general wards ($\chi^2 = 8.9$, $p = 0.012$), consistent with Tayyib and Coyer's (2016) report that ICU nurses often struggle to meet preventive care goals due to high patient acuity and documentation demands (5).

Almutairi and Moussa (2014) discovered that Saudi nurses reported knowledge but failed to execute it owing to workload and documentation difficulties (18). Our study quantifies this effect using logistic regression: each one-point increase in perceived effort lowered the likelihood of repositioning adherence by 38% (OR = 0.62, 95% CI: 0.51-0.75). These findings clearly support policy initiatives centered on personnel sufficiency, particularly in high-acuity regions. Unlike previous research that examined knowledge and practice separately (e.g., Hailu et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2021), this work fills the gap by statistically confirming the knowledge-practice link (20, 21). This integrated strategy addresses research limitations identified by Balzer et al. (2013), who noticed a dearth of implementation-focused PU prevention studies (23).

Collectively, our findings demonstrate that, while nurses usually have enough understanding of PU prevention, systemic difficulties, particularly excessive workload and documentation gaps, hinder their capacity to transform knowledge into consistent practice. Notably, documentation of repositioning had one of the lowest mean ratings ($M = 2.9$), supporting Chaboyer et al. (2016)'s concerns about poor recordkeeping as part of PU care packages (14). This breach jeopardizes both patient safety and treatment continuity.

Strengths of the Study:

- This study integrates knowledge and practice, establishing a statistical relationship between pressure ulcer knowledge and therapeutic repositioning practices.
- Context-Specific Insights: This study addresses a vacuum in South Asian and Pakistani literature by providing correlational data that is relevant to global discourse.
- Validated tools, including the Pressure Ulcer

Knowledge Assessment Tool (PUKAT 2.0) and structured self-report questions, guaranteed consistent and reliable data collection.

- Multiple levels of statistical analysis, including chi-square tests, Spearman's correlation, and logistic regression, validated the findings.

Limitations of the Study:

The study's cross-sectional methodology makes it difficult to determine the causal relationship between knowledge and adherence to repositioning procedures.

Self-Reported Practice Data: Relying on nurses' self-reported practices may lead to response bias and overestimate adherence.

Data collection was limited to a single region, making it difficult to generalize to other provinces or nations.

Clinical practices such as repositioning and recordkeeping were not validated by direct observation or audits.

Recommendations:

- Implement refresher courses focused on nutrition and interdisciplinary duties to address identified knowledge gaps.
- Audit and feedback mechanisms: Set up regular observation-based audits to verify real repositioning practices and encourage responsibility through feedback.
- Optimize nurse-to-patient ratios in ICUs to minimize pressure ulcers.
 - Simplify and integrate documentation mechanisms, such as EHR prompts or checklists, to better record repositioning interventions.

Conclusion:

This study found a substantial beneficial link between nurses' awareness of pressure ulcer prevention and adherence to repositioning measures. While overall knowledge levels were good, deficits in nutrition and transdisciplinary roles persisted. Nurses with higher education and more clinical experience demonstrated greater adherence to suggested procedures. However, high workloads, particularly in ICU settings, posed a significant impediment to continuous repositioning. The findings underscore the importance of focused education, supportive personnel policies, and better documentation techniques. Strengthening knowledge and system-

level assistance can help to bridge the gap between theory and clinical practice in pressure ulcer prevention.

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